

4-Heterocyclic Amino- α -Substituted-o-Cresols : Part II. Synthesis and Absorption Characteristics of 5, 6 and 7-Chloro-2 : 8-Dimethyl-4 (3'-Substituted Aminomethyl-4-Hydroxy Anilino) Quinolines

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The titled compounds have been synthesised, (i) by condensing 5-, 6-and 7-chloro-2 : 8-dimethyl-4-chloro quinoline derivatives respectively with 3 diethylaminomethyl, 3-piperidinomethyl and 3-morpholinomethyl-4-hydroxy anilines and (ii) by the Mannich condensation of the appropriately substituted 4 (*p*-hydroxy anilino) quinoline derivatives with paraformaldehyde and the required secondary amine. The ultraviolet spectra of these compounds have been studied.

In the previous communication in this series, syntheses and the ultraviolet spectra of 2 : 7-dimethoxy and 2-methoxy-5-methyl-8-chloro-9 (3'-substituted methyl-4'-hydroxy anilino) acridine derivatives have been described.¹ The present communication deals with the syntheses and the ultraviolet spectral study of 5-, 6-and 7-chloro-2 : 3-dimethyl-4 (3'-substituted methyl-4'-hydroxy anilino) quinoline derivatives. Like chloroquine and camoquine,² the 5-and 7-chloro derivatives contain a chlorine atom in a position meta with respect to the ring-nitrogen. These compounds have been synthesised by two alternate methods. One of the methods

- (iv) 7-chloro... .. [(X), (XI), (XII)]
 (v) 6-chloro... .. [(XIII), (XIV), (XV)]
 (vi) 5-chloro... .. [(XVI), (XVII), (XVIII)]
 (- N< = diethylamino, piperidino or morpholino)

comprises condensation of a properly substituted 4-chloro quinoline derivative with

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TABLE 1
5, 6, 7-Chloro 2 : 8 Dimethyl 4 (3'-Substituted Aminomethyl-4' Hydroxy Anilino) Quinolines

Comps. No.	R	R'	Free base m. p. °C	Formula	Analysis of free base		Dihydrochloride m. p. °C	Formula	Analysis of %Nitrogen		Dihydrochloride Equivalent Wt.	
					% Nitrogen Found	% Nitrogen Required			Found	Required	Found	Required
(X)	7-Chloro	diethylamino	130-31	$C_{23}H_{26}N_2OCl$	10.8	10.9	260-61 (d)	$C_{23}H_{28}N_2OCl_2$	9.4	9.2	266	228
(XI)	7-Chloro	piperidino	150-51	$C_{23}H_{26}N_2OCl$	10.6	10.6	200 (d)	$C_{23}H_{28}N_2OCl_2$	9.1	8.9	231	234
(XII)	7-Chloro	morpholino	218-19	$C_{23}H_{24}N_2O_2Cl$	10.4	10.6	258-59 (d)	$C_{23}H_{26}N_2OCl_2$	8.8	8.9	237	235
(XIII)	6-Chloro	diethylamino	120**	$C_{23}H_{26}N_2OCl$	10.7	10.9	270 (d)	$C_{23}H_{28}N_2OCl_2$	9.0	9.2	225	228
(XIV)	6-Chloro	piperidino	136-37	$C_{23}H_{26}N_2OCl$	10.4	10.6	235 (d)	$C_{23}H_{28}N_2OCl_2$	8.8	8.9	236	234
(XV)	6-Chloro	morpholino	192-93	$C_{23}H_{24}N_2O_2Cl$	10.7	10.6	285 (d)	$C_{23}H_{26}N_2O_2Cl_2$	9.1	8.9	233	235
(XVI)	5-Chloro	diethylamino	*	—	—	—	235-36 (d)	$C_{23}H_{28}N_2OCl_2$	9.06	9.2	230	228
(XVII)	5-Chloro	piperidino	115	$C_{23}H_{26}N_2OCl$	10.3	10.6	140 (d)**	$C_{23}H_{28}N_2OCl_2$	9.1	8.9	232	234
(XVIII)	5-Chloro	morpholino	161-62	$C_{23}H_{24}N_2O_2Cl$	10.3	10.6	178 (d)	$C_{23}H_{26}N_2O_2Cl_2$	8.7	8.9	238	235

* The base could not be purified.

** m.p. of the sample dried at 100°.

a 3-substituted methyl-4-hydroxy aniline in dilute aqueous hydrochloric acid solution³ and the other method is based on Mannich reaction between a properly substituted 4 (*p*-hydroxy anilino) quinoline derivative with paraformaldehyde and an appropriate secondary amine.⁴

2-Methyl-3-chloro aniline⁵ was condensed with ethyl acetoacetate in presence of a trace of hydrochloric acid and β (2-methyl-3-chloro) anilino crotonate formed, was cyclodehydrated by pouring it in a previously heated paraffin oil under the conditions of Conrad-Limpach reaction¹ to obtain 2 : 8-dimethyl-7-chloro-4-hydroxy quinoline (I). Following this procedure and starting with 2-methyl-4-chloro⁶ and 5-chloro⁷ anilines, 2 : 8-dimethyl-6-chloro (II) and 2 : 8-dimethyl-5-chloro (III)-4-hydroxy quinolines were synthesised. These 4-hydroxy quinoline derivatives (I), (II) and (III) dissolved readily in hot dilute alkali solution and this property was used in their purification. They, however, had a very low solubility in dilute acid solution indicating that they were probably very weak bases.

The 4-hydroxy quinoline derivatives (I), (II) and (III) when refluxed with phosphorus oxychloride afforded 4 : 7-dichloro (IV), 4 : 6-dichloro (V) and 4 : 5-dichloro (VI) 2 : 8-dimethyl quinoline derivatives. These were sufficiently stable and could be preserved and crystallised from usual solvents without their undergoing any deterioration.

2 : 8-Dimethyl-7-chloro-4 (3'-diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxy anilino) quinoline (X) and the corresponding 3'-piperidinomethyl (XI) and 3'-morpholinomethyl (XII) analogues were synthesised by condensing 2 : 8-dimethyl-4 : 7-dichloro quinoline (IV) with 3-diethylaminomethyl, 3-piperidinomethyl and 3-morpholinomethyl-4-hydroxy aniline derivatives respectively in hydrochloric acid solution. These 4-anilino quinoline derivatives, (X), (XI) and (XII) have also been synthesised by the Mannich condensation of 2 : 8-dimethyl-7-chloro-4 (*p*-hydroxy anilino) quinoline (VII) with paraformaldehyde and diethylamine, piperidine and morpholine respectively. Following these procedures and starting with (V) and (VI), the corresponding 4 (3'-substituted methyl-4'-hydroxy anilino) quinoline derivatives (XIII) to (XVIII), described in the table 1, have been synthesised. The 5-, 6- and 7-chloro-2 : 8-dimethyl-4 (*p*-hydroxy anilino) quinoline derivatives required as starting materials for the synthesis based on Mannich reaction, were prepared by condensing the corresponding 4-chloro quinoline derivatives (IV), (V) and (VI) respectively with *p*-hydroxy aniline in dilute acid solution.

The ultraviolet spectral data of 5-, 6- and 7-chloro-2 : 8-dimethyl-4 (3'-substituted methyl-4'-hydroxy anilino) quinolines in ethanol are summarised in table-2. The

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5. P. Cohn, *Mantash. Chem.*, 1900, **22**, 481.
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7. Goldschmidt Hönig, *Ber.*, 1886, **19**, 2440.

TABLE 2

Ultraviolet Spectral Data of 5, 6, 7-Chloro 2 : 8-Dimethyl-4-Substituted Anilino Quinoline Derivatives

Comps. No.	Substituent	λ max $m\mu$	log ϵ	λ max $m\mu$	log ϵ	λ max $m\mu$	log ϵ
(X)	2 : 8-dimethyl-7-Chloro-4-(R ₁) q.	230	4.64	250 ^{(In)*}	4.36	332	4.11
(XI)	2 : 8-dimethyl-7-Chloro-4-(R ₂) q.	230	4.64	251 ^(In)	4.38	332	4.14
(XII)	2 : 8-dimethyl-7-Chloro-4-(R ₃) q.	230	4.66	251 ^(In)	4.36	332	4.12
(XIII)	2 : 8-dimethyl-6-Chloro-4-(R ₁) q.	225	4.68	249 ^(In)	4.39	330	4.08
(XIV)	2 : 8-dimethyl-6-Chloro-4-(R ₂) q.	225	4.69	249 ^(In)	4.39	330	4.09
(XV)	2 : 8-dimethyl-6-Chloro-4-(R ₃) q.	225	4.69	249 ^(In)	4.39	330	4.06
(XVII)	2 : 8-dimethyl-5-Chloro-4-(R ₃) q.	230	4.63	250 ^(In)	4.40	335	4.11
(XVIII)	2 : 8-dimethyl-5-Chloro-4-(R ₃) q.	230	4.59	250 ^(In)	4.33	335	4.14

N. B. (R₁),-(R₂)-and (R₃) refer to-3'-diethylaminomethyl-3'-piperidinomethyl-, and-3'-morpholinomethyl-4'-hydroxy anilino respectively.

*^(In)=Infection.

spectra of 5-, 6- and 7-chloro-2 : 8-dimethyl-4 (3'-morpholinomethyl-4-hydroxy anilino) quinolines have been shown in the figure-1. Examination of these spectral

Fig. 1. 5-chloro- ; 6-chloro-, 7-chloro-2 : 8-dimethyl-4 (3'-morpholine-4'-hydroxy anilino) quinolines.

data and the curves reveals that the spectrum of the compounds, listed in table-2 comprises three bands, a short-wavelength high intensity band appearing in the

range from 225 to 230 $m\mu$ with $\log \epsilon$ value ranging from 4.59 to 4.69 ; and an inflection near about 250 $m\mu$ with $\log \epsilon$ ranging from 4.40 and a long-wavelength band in the range from 330 to 335 $m\mu$ and of comparatively lower intensity with $\log \epsilon$ value ranging from 4.08 to 4.39. The corresponding bands in the spectra of any of the 4-substituted anilino-2- : 8-dimethyl quinolines of 5-, 6- or 7-chloro series appear at the same wavelength and have almost the same $\log \epsilon$ value. This is expected as all the members of any particular series have essentially the same chromophoric system. The corresponding 4-substituted anilino quinolines of the three different series do not differ markedly with regard to the position of absorption maximum and the corresponding $\log \epsilon$ values.

EXPERIMENTAL

2 : 8-Dimethyl-7-chloro 4-hydroxy quinoline (I) :—A mixture of 2 methyl-3-chloro aniline⁵ (5.0 g.) and ethyl acetoacetate (5.0 ml.) containing three to four drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid was left for 24 hrs. with intermittent stirring and extracted with ether after diluting it with water (50. ml.). Ethyl- β (2-methyl-3-chloro) anilino crotonate (2.5 g.) obtained as a thick liquid on removing ether by evaporation, was poured in liquid paraffin (30 ml.) previously heated to 260°, at such a rate as to maintain the temperature between 250-55°. Heating was continued at the same temperature for five minutes after addition was complete. The solid product obtained on dilution of the cooled reaction-mixture with petroleum ether (50 ml.) was filtered and washed free from adhering paraffin with petroleum ether. The solid product was crystallised from alcohol, white granules, m.p. 305-6°, yield : 1.2 g. (Found : N, 6.6 ; Cl, 17.4 ; $C_{11}H_{10}ONCl$ requires N, 6.7 ; Cl, 17.1%).

2 : 8-Dimethyl-6-chloro-4-hydroxy quinoline (II) :—It was synthesised as described above starting with 2-methyl-4-chloro aniline⁶. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol, pale brown tiny needles, m.p. 310-11°, yield : 2.5 g. (Found : N, 6.8 ; Cl, 17.3 ; $C_{11}H_{10}ONCl$ requires N, 6.7 ; Cl, 17.1%).

2 : 8-Dimethyl-5 chloro-4-hydroxy quinoline (III) :—It was obtained as described above starting with 2-methyl-5 chloro aniline⁷. It was crystallised from dilute alcohol, yellowish tiny needles, m.p. 290-91°, yield : 1.5 g. (Found : N, 6.7, Cl, 17.4 ; $C_{11}H_{10}ONCl$ requires N, 6.7 ; Cl, 17.1%).

2 : 8-Dimethyl-4 : 7 dichloro quinoline (IV) :—A mixture of 2 : 8-dimethyl-7-chloro-4-hydroxy quinoline (I) (5.0 g.) and phosphorus oxychloride (20 ml.) was refluxed on an oil bath at 120° for 2½ hrs. Excess of phosphorus oxychloride was removed by extracting the cooled reaction mixture with petroleum ether. The residue was poured in ice-water. 2 : 8-Dimethyl-4 : 7-dichloroquinoline obtained as a light brown powder on making the reaction mixture alkaline with dilute ammonia, was collected and dried in air. It was crystallised from benzene, tiny brownish needles, m.p. 92-93°, yield : 3.5 g. (Found : N, 6.3 ; $C_{11}H_9NCl_2$; requires N, 6.2%).

2 : 8-Dimethyl-4 : 6-dichloro quinoline (V) :—This was formed on treating 2 : 8-dimethyl-6-chloro-4-hydroxy quinoline (II) with phosphorus oxychloride. It was crystallised from benzene, tiny yellowish needles, m.p. 122-23°. (Found : N, 6.4 ; $C_{11}H_9NCl_2$ requires N, 6.2%).

2 : 8-Dimethyl 4 : 5-dichloro quinoline (VI) :—This was formed on treating 2 : 8-dimethyl 5 chloro-4 hydroxy quinoline (III) with phosphorus oxychloride. It was crystallised from benzene-chloroform mixture, m.p. 86.88°. (Found : N, 6.05 ; $C_{11}H_9NCl_2$ requires N, 6.2%).

2 : 8-Dimethyl-7-chloro-4-(p-hydroxy anilino) quinoline (VII) :—A mixture of 2 : 8 dimethyl—4 : 7-dichloro quinoline (IV) (4.5 g.), *p*-aminophenol (2.2 g.) and dilute hydrochloric acid (30 ml., 20%) was heated on a water bath for 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and treated with excess of ammonia solution. The product which separated out was filtered, washed and dried in air. It was crystallised from alcohol, clusters of yellowish needles, m. p. 250-51°. (Found : N, 9.2 ; $C_{17}H_{15}N_3OCl$ requires N, 9.4%).

2 : 8-Dimethyl 6 chloro-4-(p-hydroxy anilino) quinoline (VIII) :—It was formed on condensing 2 : 8-dimethyl-4 : 6 dichloro quinoline (V) with *p*-amino phenol, It was crystallised from acetone, colourless clusters of needles, m.p. 212-13°. (Found : N, 9.5 ; $C_{17}H_{15}N_3OCl$ requires, N, 9.4%).

2 : 8-Dimethyl-5-chloro-4-(p-hydroxy anilino) quinoline (IX) :—It was synthesised by condensing 2 : 8-dimethyl-4 : 5-dichloro quinoline (VI) with *p*-amino phenol. It was crystallised from alcohol, pinkish powder, m. p. 198-99°. (Found : N, 9.1 ; $C_{17}H_{15}N_3OCl$ requires N, 9.4%).

2 : 8-Dimethyl-7-chloro-4-(3'-diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxy anilino) quinoline(X) ; —A mixture of 3-diethylaminomethyl 4-hydroxy acetanilide (2.36 g.) and hydrochloric acid (7 ml., 20%) was refluxed at 125° for 1 hr. After cooling, the solution mixture was treated with 20 percent caustic soda solution till it remained just acidic to congo red paper. Then 2 : 8-dimethyl-4 : 7-dichloro quinoline (2.26 g.) was added and the reaction mixture was heated on a steam bath for 2 hrs. After cooling, the reaction mixture was treated with ammonia solution, when 2 : 8-dimethyl-7-chloro-4-(3'-diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxy anilino) quinoline separated out. It crystallised from alcohol, white granules, m.p. 130-31°, yield : 1.5 g. (Found : N, 10.7 ; $C_{22}H_{26}N_3OCl$ requires N, 10.9%).

The dihydrochloride of (X) which separated as a crystalline powder from its acetone solution on treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid, melted at 260—61° with decomposition. (Found : N, 9.4 ; Eq. wt., 224) ; $C_{22}H_{28}N_3OCl_2$ requires N, 9.2% ; Eq.wt., 228.)

Mannich condensation of 2 : 8-dimethyl-7-chloro-4-(p-hydroxy anilino) quinoline with diethylamine and paraformaldehyde : Formation of 2 : 8-dimethyl-7-chloro-4-(3'-diethylaminomethyl-4'-hydroxy anilino) quinoline (X) :

To a solution of diethylamine (0.75 g.) in alcohol (10 ml.), a mixture of 2 : 8-dimethyl-7-chloro-4-(p-hydroxy anilino) quinoline (3.0 g.) and paraformaldehyde (0.3 g.) was added portionwise ; the reaction mixture was stirred well after each addition. It was then refluxed on a steam bath for 5 hrs. The crude product obtained on distilling off the excess of alcohol from the reaction mixture was extracted with dry acetone. On adding concentrated hydrochloric acid to the acetone extract, the dihydrochloride of 2:8 dimethyl-7-chloro-4-(3'-diethylamino methyl-4'-hydroxy anilino) quinoline separated out. The free base obtained on treating this hydrochloride with ammonia solution, crystallised from alcohol, white granules, m.p. 130.31° ; yield : 1.0 g. The mixed melting point with the same obtained by the condensation of 2 : 8-dimethyl-4 : 7-dichloro quinoline with 3-diethylaminomethyl 4-hydroxy aniline remained undepressed.

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